

Research Article

Low-cost 3D-Printed Flow Cell Biosensor for Pathogenic Escherichia Coli Bacteria Detection

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Abstract: This research seeks to develop an innovative 3D-printed biosensor for the rapid and accurate detection of Escherichia coli (*E. coli*) bacteria in water samples. *E. coli* contamination represents a significant public health risk, necessitating timely and precise detection methods. Existing techniques are often labor-intensive, expensive, and time-consuming, requiring advanced laboratory facilities and specialized personnel. The proposed biosensor will incorporate a flow cell design, which allows continuous monitoring and efficient detection of *E. coli* in real-time. The sensor will be fabricated using conductive polymer-based materials integrated with specific biological recognition elements to ensure high sensitivity and specificity. The 3D printing technology will be utilized to create a precise and reproducible flow cell structure, optimizing the sensor's functionality and scalability. The research will proceed through several key phases: designing and simulating the flow cell structure, selecting and functionalizing the sensing materials, fabricating the biosensor using 3D printing techniques, and conducting extensive testing with water samples containing various concentrations of *E. coli*. This project will make significant contributions to the field of biosensor technology, providing a practical solution for improving water quality monitoring and safeguarding public health. This research will establish a foundation for future advancements in portable and effective biosensing devices, offering a valuable tool for early detection and prevention of bacterial contamination.

Keywords: Escherichia Coli; Biosensor; Flow Cell Design; 3D printing.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Escherichia coli (*E. coli*) is a diverse group of bacteria commonly found in the intestines of humans and warm-blooded animals. While most *E. coli* strains are harmless and play a crucial role in maintaining intestinal health, some strains can cause severe food poisoning, urinary tract infections, and even life-threatening conditions such as hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS). These pathogenic strains are a significant public health concern, particularly in environments where food and water contamination are prevalent.

Traditional methods for detecting *E. coli* contamination, such as culture-based techniques and polymerase chain reaction (PCR), while effective, are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and require specialized laboratory equipment. These limitations create a demand for more efficient, portable, and real-time detection methods. Biosensors offer a promising solution, providing the capability to detect *E. coli* rapidly and accurately without the need for extensive sample preparation or sophisticated instrumentation. The development of biosensors for *E. coli* detection addresses several critical needs involving speed, portability, sensitivity, and cost-effectiveness (Huang et al., 2022). In this case, rapid detection can prevent the spread of contamination and enable timely interventions. Field-deployable sensors allow on-site testing in various environments, from food processing plants to remote water sources. High sensitivity ensures the detection of low bacterial concentrations, while specificity ensures that the sensor targets *E. coli* strains accurately without cross-reacting with other microorganisms.

Flow cell biosensors based on electrochemical structure have emerged as a superior design for detecting bacterial contamination Figure 1. The flow cell structure offers several advantages that include continuous monitoring, enhanced sensitivity, improved response time, and reduced fouling (Damiati & Schuster, 2020; Stilman et al., 2022). The flow cell design allows for the continuous flow of samples through the sensor, enabling real-time monitoring and immediate detection of contaminants (Domingo-Roca et al., 2023). The continuous flow ensures that fresh samples are constantly exposed to the sensing elements, increasing the likelihood of detecting bacteria even at low concentrations.

Figure 1. Basic construction of electrochemical flow cell sensor

This research will leverage 3D printing technology in biosensor production Figure 2. 3D printing allows for the precise and reproducible creation of complex sensor structures that would be challenging to produce using traditional manufacturing methods (Siller et al., 2020). Key benefits of using 3D printing for biosensor production include customization, scalability, precision, and material versatility. In this case, 3D printing enables the design and production of biosensors tailored to specific applications and requirements. 3D printing supports a wide range of materials, including biocompatible polymers and conductive materials, essential for the construction of functional biosensors.

Figure 2. Sensor fabrication via 3D printing technique

Potassium chloride (KCl) is the most widely used supporting electrolyte solution for application in cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments because of high aqueous solubility and good conductor (Xu et al., 2022), providing optimum ionic strength and enhancing solution conductivity. This minimizes uncompensated resistance and leads to greater accuracy and reproducibility in electrochemical measurement. In addition to that, chloride ions in KCl are able to stabilize some metal cations via complex formation, influencing their electrochemical reactions.

Nickel (II) phthalocyanine-tetrasulfonic acid tetrasodium salt (NiTsPc) is a water-soluble chemical having a stable planar structure Figure 3. Its four sulfonate groups allow it to dissolve in water, making it suitable for a variety of applications. NiTsPc is commonly used to construct nanostructures such as thin films with layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly. This experiment will utilize a combined solution of Potassium Chloride (KCl) and nickel (II) phthalocyanine-tetrasulfonic acid tetrasodium salt (NiTsPc) as the water sample for cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments and biosensor testing.

Figure 3. Molecular structures of NiTsPc

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Design and selection of sensing materials

The initial phase of the research involves the conceptualization and optimization of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor's design. This begins with an extensive literature review to understand the current advancements and limitations in biosensor technology, particularly focusing on flow cell designs. Using computer-aided design (CAD) software, detailed models of the flow cell structure will

be created, incorporating microfluidic channels and sensor integration points to facilitate optimal fluid dynamics and bacterial interaction Figure 4 (Miller & Patel, 2024; Ramiah Rajasekaran et al., 2020).

The second phase focuses on the selection and functionalization of conductive polymer-based materials to be used in the biosensor. The process begins by identifying and testing various conductive polymers suitable for 3D printing and biosensing applications. Fluid dynamics simulations will be conducted to analyse and refine the flow patterns, shear stress, and bacteria transport mechanisms within the flow cell. Initial prototypes will be fabricated using 3D printing technology to test the feasibility and practicality of the design. The outcome of this phase will be a validated and optimized flow cell structure that ensures efficient fluid dynamics, setting a solid foundation for the subsequent phases of biosensor development.

Figure 4. Schematic of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor's design

2.2 Setup for the cyclic voltammetry (CV) testing

This phase began with the preparation of the cyclic voltammetry (CV) setup to evaluate its performance on the water samples Figure 5. The Analog Device ADALM1000 was used to demonstrate the relationship between current, voltage, and impedance (including resistance, inductance, and capacitance). When connected to a laptop or tablet, the ADALM1000 functioned as a personal portable laboratory (Hall et al., 2023). Pixelpulse2, an open-source program, provided a user interface for visualizing and adjusting signals while analyzing systems connected to the device.

The CV setup included three different electrode materials: 1) platinum (Pt) as the counter electrode, which was connected to the GND of the ADALM1000, 2) graphite (Gr) as the working electrode, which was connected to the CHA of the ADALM1000, and 3) silver chloride (AgCl) as the reference electrode, which was connected to the CHB of the ADALM1000. For the preparation of the water sample used to systematically evaluate the CV's performance, the experiment utilized two solutions consisting of: 1) 40 mL of 3M KCl combined with 3 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc, and 2) 40 mL of 3M KCl combined with 6 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc.

Figure 5. Setup for the cyclic voltammetry (CV) testing

2.3 Setup for the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor testing

The experiment continued with the preparation of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor setup to evaluate its performance on the water samples Figure 6. In this phase, only the CV component was replaced with the biosensor, while the other devices remained the same for data evaluation.

The biosensor also contained three different electrodes: 1) the counter electrode was connected to the GND of the ADALM1000, 2) the working electrode was connected to the CHA of the ADALM1000, and 3) the reference electrode was connected to the CHB of the ADALM1000. The biosensor was tested by before and after applying a solution of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc onto its conductive surface to obtain the readings.

The biosensor's performance was rigorously compared with conventional detection methods to validate its effectiveness and highlight its advantages. This phase aimed to generate comprehensive data demonstrating the biosensor's high sensitivity, specificity, and reliability in detecting *E. coli*.

Figure 6. Setup for the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor testing

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Fabrication of the biosensor using 3D printing

The research is centered on the actual fabrication of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor using advanced 3D printing techniques Figure 7 (Domingo-Roca et al., 2022). High-resolution Bambu Lab A1

mini 3D printers will be employed to fabricate the optimized flow cell structure, ensuring precise replication of the design developed in the first phase (Ma et al., 2024). The integration of the functionalized sensing materials into the 3D-printed flow cell structure is a critical step, requiring precise alignment and secure attachment to maintain the sensor's functionality (Hussan K S et al., 2024). The complete assembly of the biosensor will also include necessary electronic components for signal transduction and data acquisition. Throughout this process, rigorous quality control tests will be conducted to verify the structural integrity and functionality of the biosensor components. This phase will culminate in a fully assembled and functional 3D-printed flow cell biosensor, poised for performance evaluation and testing. The use of 3D printing technology not only ensures high precision and customization but also offers a cost-effective and scalable approach to biosensor production (Remaggi et al., 2022).

Figure 7. (a) The advanced 3D printing techniques, and (b) The actual fabrication of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor

3.2 Testing on the cyclic voltammetry (CV)

The CV graph illustrated the response of how the current changed as the voltage was scanned in both the forward and reverse directions Figure 8. The solution for this experiment was prepared using 40 mL of 3M KCl combined with 3 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc. The results indicated variations in current as the voltage was applied in both directions. It showed that there were no clear peaks of oxidation and reduction available because the electrolyte solution might be insufficient at low concentration. Despite these fluctuations, the graph demonstrated the ability to form a distinguishable cyclic voltammetry. The current (A) ranged from approximately -0.035 to 0.04 A, while the voltage (V) varied between 0 and 3 V.

Figure 8. CV's graph of 40 mL of 3M KCl with 3 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc

This part showed the typical shape with an oxidation (anodic) and reduction (cathodic) peak illustrating the electroactivity of the system Figure 9. Red lines showed the slope of different regions

with response to the change in the current, and green arrows showed the voltage readings for oxidation was 2.2 V and reduction was 0.9 V. The solution for this experiment was prepared with 40 mL of 3M KCl with 6 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc, and this could have impacted the electron transfer process and enhanced the electroactivity of the sensor. The current (A) ranged from approximately -0.027 to 0.03 A, while the voltage (V) varied between 0 and 3 V. The shape of the cyclic voltammety showed excellent electron transfer characteristics, as reflected by the relatively symmetrical oxidation and reduction peaks.

Figure 9. CV's graph of 40 mL of 3M KCl with 6 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc

3.3 Testing on the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor

As stated in the method, the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor was tested before and after the electrolyte solution was applied. Figure 10 displayed the graph obtained when the biosensor was tested without any solution. The result showed that the voltage (V) ranged from 0 to 0.5 V, remaining nearly constant at Channel B across each cycle.

Figure 10. Biosensor's graph without any solution

Next, the solution for this experiment was prepared using 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc, then applied to the biosensor to obtain the graph Figure 11. The results showed that the voltage (V) ranged from 0 to 1.4 V. A clear change was detected as the peaks increased, indicating that the biosensor exhibited conductive capability in detecting the solution.

Figure 11. Biosensor's graph with the solution of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc

4. DISCUSSION

The CV experiment achieved voltage readings of 2.2 V for oxidation and 0.9 V for reduction. The results indicated that the minimum electrolyte concentration required to obtain distinct oxidation and reduction peaks were 40 mL of 3M KCl mixed with 6 mL of 0.1M KCl + 0.5 mg/mL of NiTsPc. When a lower concentration was used, no significant reaction was observed. In the biosensing experiment, the results demonstrated that the fabricated 3D-printed biosensor generated a response upon contact with electrolyte solutions. It could be concluded that the fabrication of the 3D-printed flow cell biosensor using advanced 3D printing techniques achieved early success, as it was a low-cost, disposable, biodegradable, and mass-producible alternative to conventional methods. This suggests that the biosensor could serve as a practical alternative for detecting various water samples in real-life applications such as detecting *E. coli* or any bacterial disease.

5. CONCLUSION

To summarise, this research proposes a unique and interdisciplinary technique for detecting *E. coli* that combines 3D printing technology, innovative flow cell design, new material functionalisation, and the precise use of fluid dynamics. The designed biosensor is highly sensitive and specific that allows real-time and continuous monitoring, rendering it cost-effective and efficient. 3D printing not only does the biosensor become scalable and low-cost, but it is also simple to customize to any particular application or setting. This approach addresses key limitations of conventional biosensors, including poor selectivity, difficult fabrication, and lack of flexibility. This research further highlights the power of cross-disciplinary science, drawing upon expertise in microbiology, materials science, and engineering to address an important public health issue. Thus, it provides a strong foundation for the future advancement of biosensor technologies with excellent potential for enhancing water safety, disease management, and environmental monitoring.

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